

Grape marc biotransformation to protein-rich food ingredients using fungal fermentation

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ABSTRACT

The increasing global population and rising environmental and nutritional demands require sustainable, alternative protein sources. This study explores the biovalorization of grape marc, a by-product of winery and distillery industries, as cultivation medium for edible filamentous fungi to produce protein-rich biomass for food applications. Three fungal strains, *Neurospora intermedia*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, and *Rhizopus oryzae*, were cultivated at three scales: shake flasks, bench-scale (4.5 L), and demo-scale (1300 L) bubble column reactors. Hydrothermal pretreatment (121 °C, 20 min) was applied to grape marc (GM) prior to fermentation under varying GM concentrations (2–8 % w/v), pH (3.88–6), cultivation times (48–72 h), and supplementation (vitamins, trace metals, yeast extract). The fungal biomass was analyzed for physicochemical properties, crude protein and fat, amino acid and fatty acid profiles, minerals, and polyphenols. The fungal biomass yields reached up to 4.4 g dry weight/L, with crude protein contents up to 60 % dry weight, notably with *N. intermedia*. Fungal biomass exhibited a complete essential amino acid profile, with high leucine and lysine levels, along with favorable fatty acid, minerals and polyphenols. This study demonstrates the feasibility of producing sustainable, protein-rich fungal biomass from GM, offering a valuable solution for food applications within a circular bioeconomy.

1. Introduction

In the face of multiple interlinked crises, ranging from climate change to resource scarcity, the need for sustainable resource use, while ensuring access to high-quality food for a growing population remains a critical priority. A promising response to this challenge lies in the development of novel food products based on alternative protein and nutrient sources. Ingredients derived from algae, filamentous fungi, yeast, bacteria, and insects are gaining traction in the food industry, particularly when cultivated on agro-industrial by-products.

The winemaking industry supports global wine production of approximately 237 million hectoliters (Mhl), with Europe contributing around 144.5 Mhl in 2023 (OIV, 2024). This important segment of EU agriculture generates approximately 20 million tons of solid and liquid waste annually, with Europe accounting for 14.5 million tons. The primary oenological by-product of winemaking is grape marc (GM), which represents 20–30 % of processed grapes and accounts for up to 60 % of the total solid waste from winemaking (Niculescu & Ionete, 2023). The quantity and composition of GM vary depending on grape variety, processing methods, and regional practices. GM contains alcohol,

polyphenols, tannins, pigments, unfermented sugars, and other valuable compounds, making it a promising resource for developing value-added products. Proper valorization of GM is crucial for supporting sustainability, reducing environmental impact, and advancing the circular bioeconomy (Ioannidou et al., 2022).

Filamentous fungi play an important role in industrial applications due to their unique biological properties and versatility. Two groups of filamentous fungi, Zygomycetes and Ascomycetes, are particularly relevant in biorefinery studies because of their ability to grow on various low-cost substrates while yielding a wide array of valuable products (Troiano et al., 2020). *Rhizopus* is probably the best-known genus in the class of Zygomycetes fungi, which are traditionally used in fermented foods like tempeh and tofu. Among Ascomycetes, *Neurospora intermedia* is similarly known for its role in producing oncom (Ho, 1986). *Aspergillus oryzae* is one of the most well-known fungi for the industrial production of various value-added fungal products and is used for making fermented foods and beverages, including saké, shoyu (soy sauce), and miso (soybean paste) (Gomi, 2014). These fungi are Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS), and their biomass, derived through substrate conversion, holds potential for food and feed applications due to its high

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protein, fiber, and essential nutrients (Lee et al., 2024). Only a few studies have investigated grape marc or grape pomace for the cultivation of filamentous fungi such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus oryzae* (Siller-Sánchez et al., 2024), *Trametes versicolor* (Kachrimanidou et al., 2023), and *Rhizopus oryzae* (Cebrián et al., 2024).

Despite many valorization efforts, grape marc remains an underutilized resource, linked with its complex composition, variability, limited processing infrastructure, and the lack of economically viable models. This research paper aims to integrate grape marc into a fungal biorefinery model by optimizing and upscaling submerged fermentation processes to produce protein-rich fungal biomass intended for food applications. Additionally, GM has not been investigated before for the cultivation of *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Neurospora intermedia*, and *Rhizopus oryzae* in upscaled submerged fermentation processes. As the first dedicated study of its kind, it evaluated the influence of GM on both the quantity and nutritional quality of fungal biomass, while also assessing the scalability of the process. The objective is to establish protein-rich fungal biomass as a viable and valuable ingredient for innovative food formulations, while supporting the circular bioeconomy. The results provide new insights into the role of GM in fungal cultivation, facilitating sustainable, large-scale biotechnological production and offering promising solutions for the rapidly evolving alternative protein sector and food manufacturing.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Substrate

In the present study, dried grape marc (GM) was kindly sourced in November 2023 from the Acquavite distillery in Vazzola, Italy. In accordance with the producer's practices, GM used in this study was generated as follows. After the crushing and destemming process, the skins and seeds of white grapes were separated from the must, while for red grapes, they remained in contact with the must and were separated only after fermentation by pressing. The separated skins and seeds from different grape varieties underwent ensiling and fermentation, during which sugars were converted into alcohol, followed by distillation until reaching 90 °C. The resulting skins and seeds were then dried using a conventional air-drying process. Mechanical separation was applied to separate the seeds from the skins. Finally, the skins were pulverized, resulting in GM that contained primarily Prosecco/Glera grape variety skins (about 80 %), along with other grape varieties skins from the Veneto region, including red grapes.

>50 kg of GM was vacuum-packaged and stored at 4 °C during transportation and throughout the study until use. GM was hydrothermally pretreated, where solutions of GM were prepared at concentrations of 2–8 % (w/v) and treated at 121 °C for 20 min. After cooling to room temperature, the GM solutions were centrifuged and filtered to obtain the GM liquor, which then was sterilized at 121 °C for 20 min (Systec VX-95, Systec GmbH & Co. KG, 35,440 Linden, Germany) prior to cultivations.

2.2. Microorganisms

In the present study, three edible filamentous fungal strains were obtained from the Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute, Utrecht, The Netherlands, including two Ascomycetes (*Aspergillus oryzae* var. *oryzae* CBS 819.72, and *Neurospora intermedia* CBS 131.92) and one Zygomycete (*Rhizopus oryzae* var. *delemar* CBS 145.940). The fungal strains were maintained on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), containing 20 g/L glucose (Fisher Scientific, Loughborough, UK), 4 g/L potato extract and 15 g/L agar (SigmaAldrich, Buchs, Switzerland). Once the PDA plates were inoculated with fungal spores, they were incubated at 30 °C (BINDER, KB 23, Tuttlingen, Germany) for 3–5 days, followed by storage at 4 °C, for a maximum of one month. Spore suspensions were prepared by adding 20 mL of sterile Milli-Q water to each PDA plate and by releasing

the spores with a sterile L-shaped plastic spreader.

2.3. Fungal cultivations

Different factors were investigated, to optimize the cultivation conditions per *A.oryzae*, *N.intermedia* and *R. oryzae* cultivated under submerged fermentation at three scales: shake flasks, bench-scale (4.5 L), and demo-scale (1300 L) bubble column reactors (Table 1).

2.3.1. Fungal cultivations in shake flask

Batch cultivations were conducted in 250 mL baffled Erlenmeyer flasks, placed in an orbital shaking water bath (Grant OLS-Aqua Pro, UK) at 35 °C and 115 rpm. The effects of key cultivation parameters on fungal biomass and crude protein content were studied using 2–8 % (w/v) GM liquors at pH 5, under non-supplemented and supplemented conditions, and cultivated over 48 and 72 h (Table 1). To each shake flask containing 100 mL sterile GM liquor, 2 mL of spore suspension was added: 2.6×10^6 spores/mL for *N. intermedia*, 4.9×10^6 spores/mL for *A. oryzae*, and 2.5×10^7 spores/mL for *R. oryzae*.

To assess the effect of pH, cultivations were carried out using 4 % GM liquor at the initial pH of 3.88 (without adjustment), as well as at pH 5 and 6, which were monitored and maintained throughout cultivation using either 1 M NaOH or 2 M H₂SO₄ (SigmaAldrich, Darmstadt, Germany). Additionally, the effect of supplementation was tested in cultivations with 4 % GM liquor at pH 3.88, 5, and 6 over 72 h.

Supplementation with 1 mL/L vitamin solution and 10 mL/L trace metals solution (S) was also tested across cultivations using 2–8 % GM liquor at pH 5 for 72 h. Furthermore, the following supplementation conditions were evaluated during cultivations in 4 % GM liquor: 1 mL/L vitamin solution and 10 mL/L trace metals solution (S), 5 g/L yeast extract (Y), and a combination of both (YS). In addition, all fungal strains were cultivated under identical conditions using synthetic media (15 g/L glucose and 5 g/L yeast extract as the carbon and nitrogen sources, respectively), referred to as YE samples, which served as the control.

2.3.2. Fungal cultivations in 4.5 L bubble column reactors

After identifying the optimal conditions from shake flask cultivations, scale-up in bench-scale 4.5 L bioreactors (Belach Biotechnik AB, Skogås, Sweden) was performed. Cultivation parameters were set as described in Table 1. The reactors were fed with 3 L of 4 % GM liquor, and 20 mL/L spore suspension was added. The cultivation lasted for 48 h, with an aeration rate of 1 volume_{air}/volume_{media}/min (vvm) maintained throughout the cultivation, using a sintered stainless-steel air-sparger with a pore size of 90 µm. The cultivations were performed at 35 °C and at three pH levels: 3.88, 5, and 6. The pH was controlled automatically using either 2 M NaOH or 2 M H₂SO₄ (SigmaAldrich, Darmstadt, Germany).

The bioreactors and GM liquor were sterilized at 121 °C for 20 min before cultivations. To control excessive foam formation during cultivation, 500 µL/L of sterile antifoam BIOSPUMEX™ 200 K (PMC Ouvrie SAS, 62,220 Carvin, France) was added. No supplements were applied.

2.3.3. Fungal cultivations in 1300 L bubble column reactor

After identifying the optimal conditions for maximizing biomass production and protein content, the process was scaled up using a 1300 L bubble column bioreactor (Knislinge Mekaniska Verkstad AB, Kristianstad, Sweden). Cultivation parameters were set as described in Table 1, using 4 % GM liquor supplemented with 5 g/L yeast extract, at pH 5, 35 °C, and 1 vvm for 24 h. The initial pH was adjusted to 5 before sterilizing the cultivation medium with 5 M NaOH (SigmaAldrich, Darmstadt, Germany).

The pre-inoculum of *Neurospora intermedia* was prepared initially in shake flasks, and grown for 24 h, then the pre-culture was transferred to a 26 L bubble column bioreactor (Bioengineering, Wald, Switzerland) and cultivated at pH 5, 35 °C, and 1 vvm for 24 h (Table 1). Prior

Table 1
Summary of the cultivation conditions.

Configuration	Shake flasks	Shake flasks	Shake flasks ^a	BCR	BCR ^b	BCR
Capacity	250 mL	250 mL	600 mL	4.5 L	26 L	1300 L
Working volume	100 mL	100 mL	200 mL	3 L	20 L	1000 L
Substrate concentration (%, w/v)	2, 6, 8	4	4	4	4	4
Temperature (°C)	35	35	35	35	35	35
Agitation (rpm)	115	115	115	n/a	n/a	n/a
Aeration (vvm [*])	n/a	n/a	n/a	1	1	1
Supplements	NS, S	NS, S, Y, YS	Y	NS	Y	Y
pH	5	3.88, 5, 6	5	3.88, 5, 6	5	5
Cultivation time (hours)	72	48, 72	24	48	24	24
Fungus strain	<i>N.intermedia</i> , <i>A.oryze</i> , <i>R.oryzae</i>	<i>N.intermedia</i> , <i>A.oryze</i> , <i>R.oryzae</i>	<i>N.intermedia</i>	<i>N.intermedia</i> , <i>A.oryze</i> , <i>R.oryzae</i>	<i>N.intermedia</i>	<i>N.intermedia</i>

* volume of air per volume of liquid per minute, n/a: not applicable.

^{a,b} used to prepare pre-inoculum of *Neurospora intermedia* for the demo-scale cultivations; supplementation conditions: NS, no supplements; S, vitamins (1 mL/L) + trace metals (10 mL/L); Y, yeast extract (5 g/L); YS, vitamins (1 mL/L) + trace metals (10 mL/L) + yeast extract (5 g/L), BCR, bubble column reactor.

transferring the inoculation, the 1300 L bioreactor was sterilized by direct steam injection in two cycles: the first cycle involved in-situ sterilization at 130 °C for 20 min, while in the second cycle, the reactor filled with 4 % GM liquor was sterilized at 121 °C for 20 min. After cooling overnight, the pre-inoculum was transferred.

2.4. Fungal biomass harvesting

After each cultivation run in shake flasks or 4.5 L BCR, fungal biomass was harvested, filtered through a kitchen sieve with a pore size of 1 mm², and the final volume was recorded. The collected biomass was washed, and then dried at 70 °C in a drying oven (Termaks, Norway) until reaching a constant weight.

The fungal biomass collected from the 1300 L bubble column was rinsed three times with tap water and then pressed using a 12 L juice press (Bauhaus, Belp, Switzerland). It was then transferred to large zip-lock bags and stored in a freezer at -18 °C for 1–2 weeks, followed by freeze-drying (0.022 mbar, condenser at -84 °C) using a Labconco FreeZone freeze dryer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.) until reaching a constant weight. Fungal biomass yield was determined gravimetrically and expressed as g dry biomass per liter (g/L). All cultivations were performed in duplicate.

2.5. Analytical methods

2.5.1. Substrate characterization

The total solids were determined gravimetrically based on the National Renewable Energy Laboratory method (Sluiter, 2008). The ash content was determined by calcinating at 550 °C in a muffle furnace (Gallenkamp, London, UK). The carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) content of GM were determined using an Elemental Analyzer (FLASH Smart, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) with EagerSmart software. Crude protein was calculated from N content, using a factor of 6.25. The total chemical oxygen demand (COD) levels of GM liquor used for fermentation was analyzed using a COD kit (Nanocolor® COD 15,000, Düren, Germany). Glucose was analyzed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), which consisted of a Waters 2695 separation module (Waters Corporation, USA).

2.5.2. Fungal biomass pH, water activity, and color

The fungal biomass dried and milled (Retsch MM400) was analyzed for pH (Eutech pH Spear Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.), water activity (LabSwift-aw, Novasina AG), and color (CIE L* a* b*) using a Datacolor Check Spectrophotometer. The color components L* indicated lightness (scale: 0–100), a* indicated red color intensity (scale: -60 to +60), and b* indicated yellow color intensity (scale: -60 to +60). Data were processed and extracted using the software Datacolor TOOLS Plus. All measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.5.3. Determination of crude protein content and amino acids profile

The crude protein content was calculated from the nitrogen content, using a factor of 6.25. The compositional amino acid analysis was carried out as described by Trigo et al. (2021) with some modifications. To 50 mg of dried sample, 8 mL of 6 M HCl was added, followed by hydrolysis at 110 °C for 24 h using a heat block. The whole content of the tube was transferred into a volumetric flask and topped up to 10 mL with water. The hydrolysate was then diluted twenty times with 0.2 M acetic acid and filtered using a 0.2 µm syringe filter prior to analysis with LC/MS. Two microliters of all samples were run in an LC/MS system (Agilent 1100 HPLC) with a Phenomenex column (C18, 250 µm × 4.6 µm × 3 µm), coupled to an Agilent 6120 quadrupole in the SIM positive mode (Agilent Technologies). The separation was conducted at 0.7 mL/min for 40 min using different ratios of mobile phase A (3 % methanol, 0.2 % formic acid, and 0.01 % acetic acid) and mobile phase B (50 % methanol, 0.2 % formic acid and 0.01 % acetic acid). Collected data were analyzed using the MassHunter Quantitative Analysis software (version B.09.00, Agilent Technologies). Due to the acid hydrolysis, the method was not suitable to quantify tryptophan. Further, asparagine and glutamine were codetermined with aspartic acid and glutamic acid, respectively. All measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.5.4. Determination of crude fat content and fatty acids profile

The crude fat content of fungal biomass was determined through solvent extraction using a ST 243 Soxtec™ extraction unit (FOSS, Hillerød, Denmark), and petroleum ether. Fatty acid composition was determined using the method by Cavonius et al. (2014). Lipids were extracted with toluene, and heneicosanoic acid (C21:0) was used as an internal standard. Fatty acids were transesterified by adding acetyl chloride-methanol (10 %) in an ice bath and incubating at 70 °C for 2 h. Fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were extracted with petroleum ether: diethyl ether (4:1), dried under nitrogen, and dissolved in isoctane. A Clarus® 590 GC equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and capillary column was used for separation and detection. Chromatograms were analyzed using TotalChrom™ software. All measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.5.5. Determination of minerals content

Minerals such as phosphorus (P), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), magnesium (Mg), iron (Fe), and manganese (Mn) were analyzed using Microwave Plasma Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (MP-AES 4200, Agilent Technologies) as per Asadollahzadeh et al. (2018) with modifications. Samples (100 mg) were digested with HNO₃ and H₂O₂, heated at 110 °C, diluted to 10 mL with Milli-Q water, centrifuged, and filtered (0.22 µm PES). Quantifications were made using standard curves of minerals prepared from single-element solutions in 2 % HNO₃ (SigmaAldrich, Buchs, Switzerland). All measurements were conducted in triplicate.

2.5.6. Determination of total polyphenolic content

Fungal biomass extracts were prepared as described by Qin et al. (2013), with slight modifications. To 100 mg of fungal biomass was added 8 mL of ethanol:water:HCl (80:19.9:0.1 v/v/v) and vortexed for 1 min. The samples were then incubated at 37 °C for 4 h and gently mixed at 7 rpm using a rotator (SB3, Stuart). After centrifugation at 3000 × g for 1 min, the extracts were filtered through 0.22 µm filters. The total polyphenols were determined according to Singleton and Rossi (1965), where extracts were mixed with Folin–Ciocalteu reagent (1:10 v/v) and Na₂CO₃ (7.5 % w/v) in ratio 1:5:4. After incubating the samples for 30 min at room temperature and centrifuging at 18,900 × g for 2 min, the absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer (Libra, Bichrom). The results were calculated using a gallic acid calibration curve (7.5–250 ppm) and expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of fungal biomass (dry weight). All measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.6. Statistical analysis

All assays were carried out in triplicate unless otherwise stated. Results are presented as mean values ± standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was performed using Statgraphics 19 software (Statgraphics Technologies, Inc., The Plains, Virginia, USA). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and general linear models (GLM) were applied unless otherwise stated. Means showing significant differences were further analyzed using Tukey's post hoc test at a significance level of 5 %. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between pairs of variables unless otherwise specified. Statistically significant differences were considered at a p-value < 0.05 within a 95 % confidence interval.

3. Results and discussion

In the present study, dried grape marc (GM), was hydrothermally pretreated and used as 2–8 % GM liquor for the growth of three edible filamentous fungi, namely *A. oryzae*, *N. intermedia* and *R. oryzae*. To examine the scalability of the fermentation process, cultivations were conducted at laboratory, pilot and demo-scales.

3.1. Grape marc characterisation

In the present study, GM composition was characterized to identify components that could potentially influence fungal growth (Table S1). The dried GM samples exhibited a substantial total solid level (92.5 ± 0.07 %), with slightly higher lignin (31.8 ± 0.06 %) levels and lower glucose (2.93 ± 0.03 %) content compared to those reported by Suescun–Ospina et al. (2023). The crude protein was 13.4 ± 0.29 % and C:N ratio was 21.4 ± 1.69, an important factor influencing fungal growth, as highlighted by Gao et al. (2007). Crude fat content (3.06 ± 0.07 %) was lower than in other studies, likely due to the absence of grape seeds. The total ash content (5.95 ± 0.14 %) fell within the range reported in the literature, providing essential minerals that could support fungal growth. The pH values (3.88 ± 0.01) of GM were within the expected range reported in previous studies, indicating the acidic nature of GM. The total polyphenolic content (6.08 ± 0.15 mg GAE/g) of GM was lower compared to the literature data, which might be influenced from the drying processes.

3.2. Fungal biomass production

Cultivations in shake flasks were performed to determine the best growing conditions before upscaling to 4.5 L and 1300 L bubble column reactors. The effects of GM liquor concentration, pH level, cultivation duration, supplementation, and fungal strains on biomass production and crude protein content are discussed in the following sections.

3.2.1. The effect of GM liquor concentration

Out of the various concentrations (2–8 %) of GM liquor, cultivated at pH 5 and incubated for 72 h, the results indicated that both fungal biomass yield and crude protein content varied with GM liquor concentration across all fungal species (Fig. 1).

The biomass yields and protein content were as follows: 1.03–2.60 g/L and 25.2–36.7 % for *A. oryzae*, 1.65–2.78 g/L and 24.8–36.9 % for *N. intermedia*, and 0.24–1.72 g/L and 31.7–36.2 % for *R. oryzae*. Across all fungal strains, the highest biomass yield was obtained using 4 % GM liquor. The highest protein content was achieved by *N. intermedia* ($p < 0.05$) compared to other fungal strains.

For *R. oryzae*, biomass yield and crude protein content were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared to the other species. As GM liquor concentrations increased above 4 %, a decrease in fungal biomass and protein values was observed. This could be influenced by changes in the C:N ratio (Gao et al., 2007), as well by the content level of polyphenolic compounds (Bulkan et al., 2022).

Based on these results, a concentration 4 % (w/v) of GM liquor was selected for further investigation of the effects of cultivation time (48–72 h), pH (3.88–6), and supplementation with 5 g/L yeast extract (Y), and a combination of 1 mL/L vitamin solution, 10 mL/L trace metals solution, and 5 g/L yeast extract (YS), as described in the following sections.

3.2.2. The effect of GM liquor pH level

The pH of the 4 % GM liquor significantly impacted the growth rate of fungal strains. Notably, optimal fungal biomass was achieved at pH of 5 (Fig. 2). For the cultivation media with an initial pH of 3.88, no adjustments were made during fermentation. Both *R. oryzae* and *A. oryzae* were able to produce fungal biomass from 4 % GM liquor with initial pH 3.88, which ultimately reached approximately 8.0 at the end of the cultivation period. The observed increase in pH values may be attributed to the accumulation of ammonia in the medium, which can potentially affect the growth of fungi (Souza Filho et al., 2017). In the present study, *N. intermedia* did not performed well in GM liquor with initial pH 3.88, confirming other studies (Osadolor et al., 2017; Nair et al., 2016). This could be related to the presence of organic compounds in the GM cultivation medium, which may have an inhibitory effect. The pH level of GM liquor was systematically adjusted and monitored during the cultivation process for pH 5 and 6. For all fungi strains, a decrease in biomass production was observed at pH 6. It was observed that *A. oryzae*, *R. oryzae* and *N. intermedia* exhibited optimal growth at pH 5. Similar findings were reported by Osadolor et al. (2017) and Nair et al. (2016).

A strong positive correlation was observed between fungal biomass and crude protein content. The Pearson correlation coefficients were $R = 0.8550$ at pH 3.88, $R = 0.8188$ at pH 5, and $R = 0.9655$ at pH 6, all statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. The positive relationship between fungal growth and protein content was also highlighted by Asadollahzadeh et al. (2018). These results suggest that fungal biomass production can be optimized at the same time as crude protein content.

Since yeast extract provided all essential nutrients for fungal growth, the crude protein content of fungal biomass obtained from cultivations in synthetic media (YE) was higher (24–37 %) compared to the NS (non-supplemented) samples, cultivated at pH 5. However, when comparing YE with Y (samples supplemented with 5 g/L yeast extract), the crude protein content was lower (10–21 %) (Fig. 2). The higher protein content in Y samples across all fungal strains indicates the synergistic effect of both 4 % GM liquor and 5 g/L yeast extract on fungal growth.

To confirm the pH effect on the fungal growth rate, cultivations were scaled up in 4.5 L bubble column reactors, using 4 % GM liquor without supplementation, and cultivated for 42 h (Fig. 3).

The optimal fungal biomass with highest crude protein content was achieved at pH 5, which is in accordance with the cultivation results performed in shake flasks. The biomass yields and protein content ranged as follows: 1.51–1.61 g/L and 29.6–37.3 % for *A. oryzae*, 0.078–2.35 g/L and 25.92–39.97 % for *N. intermedia*, and 1.31–1.52 g/L

Fig. 1. Cultivations in shake flask using varying concentrations of GM liquor (2–8 %, w/v), conducted for 72 h at pH 5, under two conditions: NS (non-supplemented) and S (supplemented with 1 mL/L vitamin solution and 10 mL/L trace metal solution). Results show: a) fungal biomass yield, and b) crude protein content.

Fig. 2. The fungal biomass, and crude protein content for *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Neurospora intermedia*, and *Rhizopus oryzae* cultivated in shake flasks using 4 % GM liquor under varying pH conditions (3.88, 5, and 6), and supplementation conditions, using NS (non-supplemented), S (supplemented with vitamins and trace metals), Y (supplemented with yeast extract), YS (supplemented with vitamins, trace metals, and yeast extract) and YE is the fungal biomass obtained from synthetic media (grown at pH 5). Different lowercase letters (a–j) above the bars indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups, based on Tukey’s post hoc test with interaction effects considered.

and 29.35–35.2 % for *R. oryzae*. *N. intermedia* could not grow well at initial pH 3.88, as indicated by the low biomass content (0.078 ± 0.001 g/L). Lower levels of fungal biomass were obtained in bubble column reactors under the same cultivation conditions at pH 3.88 and pH 5, while higher levels were observed at pH 6. The Pearson correlation

coefficient between fungal biomass and protein content in bubble column cultivations for all fungal strains were $R = 0.9692$ at pH 3.88, $R = 0.9368$ at pH 5, and $R = 0.8849$ at pH 6.

From visual observations, it was noted that in both shake flasks and 4.5 L bubble column reactor under the same conditions, all fungal strains

Fig. 3. Cultivation in 4.5 L bubble column reactor (BCR) using 4 % GM liquor under varying pH conditions (3.88, 5, and 6). The figure shows: a) fungal biomass, and b) crude protein content for *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Neurospora intermedia*, and *Rhizopus oryzae* cultivated in shake flasks without added supplements. Different lowercase letters (a–g) above the bars indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups, based on Tukey's post hoc test with interaction effects considered.

grew as loose hyphal aggregates.

3.2.3. Effect of cultivation time and fungal strains

To evaluate the effect of cultivation duration on fungal biomass production and protein content, Erlenmeyer flask cultivations were conducted using 4 % GM liquor for all fungal strains (*A. oryzae*, *N. intermedia*, and *R. oryzae*). Experiments were performed at three pH levels (3.88, 5, and 6) under two conditions: with supplementation (S: vitamin and trace metal solution) and without supplementation (NS). The cultivation periods were 48 and 72 h, as detailed in Table 1.

A statistically significant relationship between fungal biomass production, crude protein content, and the variables fungal strain, supplementation, cultivation time, and pH (Figure S1) were identified using a General Linear Model (GLM) analysis. Fungal strains significantly affected fungal biomass production ($p < 0.05$). In addition, cultivation time had the strongest effect on both fungal biomass production ($p < 0.05$) and crude protein content ($p < 0.05$), highlighting its crucial role in obtaining protein-rich fungal biomass from 4 % GM liquor fermented by fungal strains *A. oryzae*, *N. intermedia*, and *R. oryzae*.

3.2.4. The effect of supplementation

The supplementation with 1 mL/L of vitamin and 10 mL/L of trace metal solution (S) slightly enhanced fungal biomass, averaging 6 % higher ($p < 0.05$), and protein content was up to 4 % higher ($p < 0.05$) compared with non-supplemented (NS) fungal biomass. This was consistent across all cultivation media concentrations (GM 2–8 %), pH (3.88–6), and all fungal species cultivated in shake flasks (Figs. 1 and 2). However, the differences were not considered large enough to warrant supplementation of vitamin and trace metals in the bubble column cultivations (4.5 and 1300 L).

The application of 5 g/L yeast extract significantly enhanced fungal biomass yield across all tested fungal strains (*A. oryzae*, *N. intermedia*, and *R. oryzae*) and pH levels (3.88–6) in shake flask cultivations using 4 % GM liquor (Fig. 2). Fungal biomass yield increased on average 2 times when supplemented with Y (yeast extract, $p < 0.05$) and YS (yeast extract, vitamins, trace metals, $p < 0.05$) compared to NS (non-supplemented samples), and to S (vitamins and trace metals) supplemented samples. Supplementation with 5 g/L yeast extract, 1 mL/L vitamin and 10 mL/L trace metals solution (YS) increased fungal biomass production by 5–7 % ($p < 0.05$) compared to 5 g/L yeast extract (Y) supplementation.

The crude protein content of fungal biomass, increased on average 1.6 times when supplemented with Y (yeast extract, $p < 0.05$) and YS

(yeast extract, vitamins, trace metals, $p < 0.05$) compared to NS (non-supplemented samples), and to S (vitamins and trace metals) supplemented samples. Supplementation with yeast extract, vitamins and trace metals (YS) provided only a slight further increase (1 %–4 %, $p < 0.05$) over yeast extract alone.

3.2.5. Fungal cultivation in demo-scale reactor

Based on bench scale cultivations, the optimal cultivation conditions for large-scale production were determined. These conditions include 4 % (w/v) GM liquor, pH 5, 1.0 vvm aeration, a temperature of 35 °C. Based on the results on supplementation effects on fungal growth, 5 g/L yeast extract was added. The cultivation were performed for 24 h. *N. intermedia* was selected due to its higher fungal biomass yield and crude protein content compared to other fungal strains. The cultivation resulted in a biomass production of 3.290 ± 0.001 g dry weight/L and a crude protein content of 45.40 ± 1.38 % dry weight. The protein level is similar to that of *Fusarium venenatum*, and to commercially available products derived from it, such as Quorn™ (Finnigan et al., 2019).

3.3. Fungal biomass characterization

The dried fungal biomass obtained from cultivations of *A. oryzae*, *N. intermedia*, and *R. oryzae* in 4 % (w/v) GM liquor at pH 5, without supplementation, in 4.5 L bench scale bubble column reactors for 48 h, was evaluated for its key characteristics (Tables 2 – 3 and Table S2).

3.3.1. The composition and physico-chemical properties of fungal biomass

The pH values were measured for dried fungal biomass indicating that *A. oryzae* biomass (6.40 ± 0.06) had the highest value and *R. oryzae* (5.54 ± 0.09) the lowest. Further research is needed to understand the effect of pH levels in protein-rich fungal biomass in relation to chemical and microbiological stability during storage. The water activity (a_w) of the dried fungal biomass was between 0.387–0.459, suggesting both microbiological and chemical stability (Roudaut & Debeaufort, 2011). The dried fungal biomass was subjected to color measurement (lightness, L^* ; redness, a^* and yellowness, b^*). Filamentous fungi are recognized for fungal pigments production, which are broadly classified based on the biosynthetic pathways as either polyketides or carotenoids (Abel et al., 2023). The color of fungal biomass is an important quality parameter as it makes food look more natural and sensory appealing (Singh et al., 2023). In addition, mycopigments are associated with antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity (Panchanawaporn et al., 2022).

In the present study, the color L^* value decreased with the increase in a_w . Among fungal samples *R. oryzae* was darker ($L^* 39.68 \pm 2.42$, $a_w 0.459 \pm 0.050$), and *N. intermedia* was lighter ($L^* 45.27 \pm 2.86$, $a_w 0.387 \pm 0.030$). The correlation observed between L^* (lightness) and Mg ($p < 0.05$) indicates that higher magnesium content may reduce lightness. Strong positive correlation was found between a^* (redness) and a_w ($p < 0.05$) suggesting that water activity influences color intensity. The correlation found between a^* and protein ($p < 0.05$) indicate that protein levels are linked to changes in redness and strongly impact color intensity. These findings suggest that both water activity (a_w) and protein content are critical in determining fungal biomass color, and influencing the visual appearance of the product.

Among minerals, phosphorus (P) had the highest content in all fungal strains, followed by Mg and Fe (Table 2). Correlation was found among b^* (yellowness) and P ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that an increase in phosphorus levels can decrease the yellowness, thus affecting color. Mg and Fe showed a positive correlation with a^* ($R = 0.9793$ and $R = 0.6804$) and a negative correlation with L^* and b^* , indicating that high levels of magnesium and iron increase the redness and reduce the lightness and yellowness. The correlations of minerals with color parameters and with each other play a crucial role in determining both appearance and nutritional quality of fungal biomass.

The fungal biomass showed high levels of total polyphenolic content, where *R. oryzae* had the highest level (120.5 ± 9.1 mg/g dry biomass), followed by *A. oryzae*, and *N. intermedia* (Table 2). These compounds are known for their nutritional and medicinal value, due to their unique structure and function (Yu et al., 2025). In the present study, strong positive correlations were found among total polyphenolic content and minerals such as Fe ($R = 0.9636$), P ($R = 0.9940$), Mg ($R = 0.9400$), and Mn ($R = 0.8287$). In addition, a positive correlation with a^* (redness) was found, indicating that the polyphenols could come from the GM, such as anthocyanins in red grapes (Delić et al., 2024). The incorporation of fungal biomass rich in polyphenols in new food formulation could provide consumers with functional and healthy food.

The total COD level of GM resulted 162.50 ± 0.35 g/L, which is comparable to other studies (Perra et al., 2022). The fungal cultivation of 4 % GM resulted in COD reductions of 40–47 % (Table 2). Similar ranges of total COD reduction was achieved by cultivation in potato protein liquor (Sar et al., 2022). Additionally, a positive correlations was found among COD reduction and b^* (yellowness) ($R = 0.9408$) suggesting that increased COD removal efficiency can be observed by an increase in yellowness, thus affecting the color of both fungal biomass and cultivation broth.

Table 2

Key characteristics of *A. oryzae*, *N. intermedia* and *R. oryzae* biomass.

Parameter	<i>A. oryzae</i>	<i>N. intermedia</i>	<i>R. oryzae</i>
pH	6.40 ± 0.06	6.00 ± 0.12	5.54 ± 0.09
a_w	0.422 ± 0.010	0.387 ± 0.030	0.459 ± 0.050
Color			
L^* (lightness)	43.16 ± 1.10	45.27 ± 2.86	39.68 ± 2.42
a^* (redness)	6.26 ± 0.03	5.15 ± 0.24	7.16 ± 0.13
b^* (yellowness)	11.53 ± 0.08	11.50 ± 0.28	11.35 ± 0.51
Crude protein, %	37.3 ± 0.0	40.00 ± 0.14	35.20 ± 0.35
Crude fat, %	14.50 ± 0.56	13.20 ± 0.53	16.60 ± 0.02
Minerals, mg/100 g			
P	132.4 ± 4.8	138.6 ± 24.4	204.2 ± 25.6
Mg	14.10 ± 0.36	12.60 ± 1.98	16.60 ± 1.32
Fe	3.76 ± 0.07	4.95 ± 0.20	8.59 ± 2.11
Zn	0.64 ± 0.01	2.09 ± 0.43	2.24 ± 0.42
Cu	0.08 ± 0.04	0.69 ± 0.13	0.43 ± 0.04
Mn	0.19 ± 0.01	0.27 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.13
Total polyphenolic content (mg/g)	36.20 ± 1.23	33.00 ± 1.47	120.5 ± 9.1
COD reduction, %	46.60 ± 1.44	43.60 ± 3.43	40.40 ± 3.22

Results are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD) on a dry weight basis.

3.3.2. Protein content and amino acids profile of fungal biomass

The fungal biomass obtained from 4.5 L bubble column media contained 35–40 % crude protein (Table 2 and 3), with *N. intermedia* exhibiting the highest content. However, some residual GM particles may have influenced the crude protein content measurement, leading to an underestimation of the protein levels. Variations in protein content have been observed for filamentous fungi cultivated in different substrates, including spent liquor (Asadollahzadeh et al., 2018), potato protein liquor (Sar et al., 2022), and oat flour (Rousta et al., 2022).

The amino acid composition of the fungal protein is crucial from a nutritional perspective. Among the 20 amino acids that are found in the human body, 9 are considered essential (histidine, isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, phenylalanine, threonine, tryptophan, valine), since they cannot be synthesized in the body and must be supplied through the diet (Joint WHO/FAO/UNU Expert Consultation, 2007).

Not all of the crude protein could be attributed to amino acids, which made up 11–16 % of the biomass (Table 3). The remaining portion likely consists of glucosamine derivatives found in the cell wall, along with nucleic acids (Ferreira et al., 2012), as well other nitrogen-based compounds. The amino acid content of fungal biomass might be influenced by the growing conditions, cultivation media and the fungal strain used (Rousta et al., 2022). In the present study, eight of nine essential amino acids were identified in fungal biomass. Amongst the fungi strains, the highest proportion of essential amino acids were detected in *R. oryzae*, followed by *A. oryzae*, and *N. intermedia* (Table 3). Amongst the essential amino acids, leucine and lysine are of particular interest. Leucine exhibited the highest concentration among the essential amino acids: 9.95 % in *A. oryzae*, 9.91 % in *R.oryzae* and 9.05 % in *N.intermedia*. Leucine is the most abundant amino acid in tissue and food proteins, with requirement estimated at 39 mg/kg per day. Lysine is the second most abundant essential amino acid in all fungal strains, and has daily requirements just below that of leucine, with an estimated 30 mg/kg (Joint WHO/FAO/UNU Expert Consultation, 2007).

Nine non-essential amino acids (alanines, arginines, glycines, cysteines, serines, aspartic acids, glutamic acids, prolines and tyrosines) were detected in the fungal biomass, with glutamic acids making up the largest individual portion (14.3–17.2 %). Glutamic acid is the most important amino acid in food manufacturing, known for its delicious taste (Bazaraa et al., 2016).

Table 3

The crude protein content and amino acid profiles of fungal biomass obtained from GM cultivation.

	<i>A. oryzae</i>	<i>N. intermedia</i>	<i>R. oryzae</i>
Crude protein (%)	37.3 ± 0.0	40.00 ± 0.14	35.20 ± 0.35
Total amino acids (%)	10.90 ± 0.78	16.10 ± 0.32	11.90 ± 0.32
Essential amino acids (% of total)			
Histidines	1.95 ± 0.24	1.95 ± 0.38	2.27 ± 0.36
Isoleucines	5.63 ± 0.15	5.32 ± 0.17	6.21 ± 0.34
Leucines	9.95 ± 0.29	9.05 ± 0.07	9.91 ± 0.25
Lysines	8.43 ± 0.0	9.19 ± 0.07	9.59 ± 0.23
Methionines	1.51 ± 0.08	1.73 ± 0.05	1.82 ± 0.08
Phenylalanines	5.34 ± 0.15	4.82 ± 0.12	5.49 ± 0.29
Threonines	6.35 ± 0.28	6.05 ± 0.29	6.26 ± 0.15
Valines	7.35 ± 0.17	6.82 ± 0.02	7.28 ± 0.22
Total	46.50 ± 0.85	44.90 ± 0.34	48.80 ± 1.08
Non-essential amino acids (% of total)			
Alanines	6.70 ± 0.14	6.50 ± 0.19	6.26 ± 0.11
Arginines	5.46 ± 0.79	5.57 ± 0.41	4.92 ± 0.65
Aspartic Acids	9.80 ± 0.27	10.70 ± 0.31	10.97 ± 0.27
Cysteines	0.52 ± 0.03	0.47 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.04
Glutamic Acids	16.50 ± 0.72	17.20 ± 0.51	14.30 ± 0.23
Glycines	4.59 ± 0.08	4.79 ± 0.09	4.48 ± 0.17
Prolines	4.60 ± 0.10	4.12 ± 0.07	3.72 ± 0.15
Serines	4.18 ± 0.10	4.16 ± 0.27	4.17 ± 0.16
Tyrosines	1.20 ± 0.03	1.58 ± 0.07	1.88 ± 0.27
Total	53.50 ± 0.85	55.10 ± 0.34	51.20 ± 0.81

Results are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD) on a dry weight basis.

3.3.3. The crude fat content and fatty acid profile of fungal biomass

The fungal biomass achieved after cultivation on 4 % GM contained 13.20 – 16.60 % crude fat, with the highest content being observed in *R. oryzae* (16.60 ± 0.02 %), followed by *A. oryzae* (14.50 ± 0.56 %) and *N. intermedia* (13.2 ± 0.53 %) (Table S2).

The presence of carbon sources, the C/N ratio and other nutrients in the GM cultivation medium supported the synthesis of mycelial fat. In the present study, the fungal biomass produced from GM medium resulted in higher crude fat content compared to fungal biomass obtained from cultivations in spent sulfite liquor (Asadollahzadeh et al., 2018).

Fat is an important macronutrient, responsible for about 25–30 % of the daily energy in a healthy diet. In addition, it provides essential fatty acids and facilitates the absorption of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, E, and K).

The fatty acids composition of the dried fungal biomass is presented in Table S2, grouped into three broad groups based on chemical classifications, and distinct biological properties of fatty acids of each group: saturated, monounsaturated, and polyunsaturated fatty acids. Essential fatty acids are polyunsaturated fatty acids that cannot be synthesized in the body yet are necessary for health. The fatty acid profile varied among the three fungal strains. The levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids were higher for *A. oryzae*, while *R. oryzae* had the highest level of monounsaturated fatty acids (60 %), followed by *A. oryzae* (43 %) and *N. intermedia* (~39 %). The highest level of saturated fatty acids was detected in *N. intermedia* (31 %), followed by *A. oryzae* (18.9 %) and *R. oryzae* (10.3 %). Across all fungal strains the most abundant fatty acids were oleic acid (27.91–59.13 %) and linoleic acid (19.77–38.16 %) followed by palmitic acid (7.34–27.84 %). The same trends have been observed in other studies using oat flour (Rousta et al., 2022).

Given the high crude protein content, complete essential amino acid profile, and overall nutritional value of fungal biomass produced via submerged fermentation on grape marc holds potential as a viable alternative protein source for food applications. This is supported by previous research demonstrating the versatility of fungal biomass obtained from edible filamentous fungi grown on agri-food side streams, particularly for innovative food applications (Bulkan et al., 2022; Ho, 1986; Kachrimanidou et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2024; Rousta et al., 2022; Sar et al., 2022). Future research should therefore focus on exploring the functional properties of fungal protein and developing alternative food product formulations that incorporate fungal biomass cultivated on grape marc as a protein ingredient.

4. Conclusion

This study investigates the conversion of grape marc into alternative protein sources through fermentation with filamentous fungi. Fermentation bioprocesses were optimized at bench-scale and the best cultivation conditions were scaled up to demo-scale production. Submerged fermentation using *A. oryzae*, *N. intermedia*, and *R. oryzae* successfully bioconverted grape marc into protein-rich fungal biomass with an improved nutritional profile, making it a potentially valuable ingredient for food or feed applications.

The crude protein content and amino acid composition of fungal biomass produced from grape marc meet human dietary requirements, positioning all three fungal strains as strong candidates for food applications. Additionally, the fungal biomass contained a high proportion of the essential fatty acids, particularly linoleic acid. The mineral content and other quality attributes further indicate the potential for integration into new product development. Moreover, incorporating fungal biomass with enhanced polyphenolic content could expand the functional food options.

Biovalorization of grape marc through fungal cultivation emerges as an innovative strategy for transforming winery and distillery byproducts into protein-rich fungal biomass. This approach not only delivers nutritional and functional value but also contributes to environmental

sustainability by reducing chemical oxygen demand (COD). As such, it represents a scalable and eco-efficient solution within the circular bio-economy, with the potential to drive innovation across food, feed, and bioproduct industries.

Further research should focus on assessing the techno-functional properties and quality parameters required for product development, ensuring its optimal functionality as an ingredient in alternative food products. Additionally, investigating the post-fermentation composition of the residual cultivation media may reveal valuable components, opening new avenues for value-added applications.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Luziana Hoxha: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Patrik R. Lennartsson:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation. **Mohammad J. Taherzadeh:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.focha.2025.101058](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.focha.2025.101058).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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